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UDK 612.11

ABDIYEV Kattabek MakhmatovichCandidate of Medical Sciences Associate Professor
Samarkand State Medical University**COMPLICATIONS OF PRIMARY MYELOFIBROSIS AND TACTICS OF THEIR TREATMENT** <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/Zenodo.11301052>**ABSTRACT**

Primary myelofibrosis (PM) is rare disease with newly incidence about 1 : 100 000 inhabitants per year. The names for primary myelofibrosis used before were agnogenic myeloid metaplasia, chronic idiopathic metaplasia, osteomyelofibrosis, subleukemic myelosis.

The most frequent complications of the clinical course of PMF may be: tumor intoxication, splenomegaly, anemia, infectious complications, thrombocytopenia and hemorrhagic syndrome, the presence of foci of extramedullary hematopoiesis, thrombosis, blast transformation, uric acid diathesis (secondary gout), secondary hemosiderosis.

During the study of this disease, the following results were established. For the first time as an independent nosological form of myeloproliferative disease in 1951, William Dameshek called it idiopathic or agnogenic myeloid metaplasia. Subsequently, the combination of the disease with leukocytosis, splenomegaly and bone marrow fibrosis was described in different countries as primary osteosclerosis/osteomyelofibrosis, agnogenic myeloid metaplasia, chronic idiopathic myelofibrosis, osteomyelofibrosis, subleukemic myelosis. When treating the disease, that is, primary myelofibrosis, the use of transfusions of hemocomponents containing red blood cells leads to a rapid improvement in the patient's condition and a decrease in the manifestations of anemic syndrome. At the same time, long-term use of transfusions is due to the lack of active mechanisms for removing iron from the body and the limited ability to store it in the liver, when the number of transfusions exceeds 20-25 doses, with the accumulation of iron in organs and tissues leading to the development of secondary hemosiderosis. Patients may have a high rate of development of hemosiderosis, since against the background of chronic anemia, the absorption of iron from the gastrointestinal tract increases. It has been proven that disruption of the redox process and stimulation of lipid peroxidation leads to cell damage and dysfunction of internal organs.

This article presents recommendations for the prevention and treatment of these complications.

Keywords: primary myelofibrosis, tumor intoxication, splenomegaly, anemia, infectious complications, hemorrhagic syndrome, extramedullary hematopoiesis, thrombosis, blast transformation, uric acid diathesis, secondary

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BIRLAMCHI MIYELOFIBROZNING ASORATLARI VA ULARNI DAVOLASH TAKTIKASI

ANNOTATSIYA

Birlamchi miyelofibroz (BMF) kam uchraydigan qonning tizimli kasalligi bo'lib, birinchi marta aniqlangan bemorlar soni yiliga taxminan 1:100000 aholini tashkil qiladi. Ilgari ushbu kasallikni tavsiflash uchun agnogen miyeloid metaplaziya, surunkali idiopatik miyelofibroz, osteomiyelofibroz, subleykemik miyeloz sinonimlari qo'llanilgan.

Birlamchi miyelofibrozni klinik kechishida eng ko'p uchraydigan asoratlar o'sma intoksikatsiyasi, splenomegaliya, anemiya, yuqumli asoratlar, trombotsitopeniya va gemorragik sindrom, ekstramedullar qon yaratish o'choqlari, tromboz, blast transformatsiyasi, siydik kislotasi diatezi (ikkilamchi podagra), ikkilamchi gemosideroz bo'lishi mumkin.

Ushbu kasallikni o'rganish davomida quyidagi natijalar aniqlab olindi. Birinchi marta miyeloproliferativ kasallikning mustaqil nozologik shakli sifatida 1951 yilda William Dameshek idiopatik yoki agnogen miyeloid metaplaziya deb nomlagan. Keyinchalik kasallikning leykotsitoz, splenomegaliya va suyak iligi fibrozi bilan bog'liqligi turli mamlakatlarda birlamchi osteoskleroz/osteomiyelofibroz, agnogen miyeloid metaplaziya, surunkali idiopatik miyelofibroz, osteomiyelofibroz, subleykemik miyeloz deb ta'riflangan. Kasallikni, ya'ni birlamchi miyelofibrozni davolashda tarkibida eritrotsitlar mavjud gemokomponentlar transfuziyalaridan foydalanish bemorning ahvolini tezda yaxshilashga va anemik sindromning namoyon bo'lishining kamayishiga olib keladi. Shu bilan birga, organizmda temirni yo'q qilishning faol mexanizmlari yo'qligi va uni jigarda saqlash imkoniyati cheklanganligi sababli transfuziyalardan uzoq muddat foydalanish, transfuziyalar soni 20-25 dozadan ortiq bo'lganda, a'zolar va to'qimalarda temirning to'planishi bilan tavsiflanadigan ikkilamchi gemosideroz rivojlanishiga olib keladi.

Bemorlarda gemosideroz rivojlanish darajasi yuqori bo'lishi mumkin, chunki surunkali anemiya fonida oshqozon-ichak traktidan temirning so'rilishi kuchayadi. Oksidlanish – tiklanish holatining buzilishi, lipidlarning peroksidli oksidlanishining rag'batlantirilishi hujayralarning zararlanishiga va ichki a'zolarining disfunktsiyasiga olib kelishi isbotlangan.

Maqolada ushbu asoratlarning profilaktikasi va davolash bo'yicha tavsiyalar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: birlamchi miyelofibroz, o'sma intoksikatsiyasi, splenomegaliya, anemiya, yuqumli asoratlar, gemorragik sindrom, ekstramedullar qon yaratish o'choqlari, tromboz, blast transformatsiyasi, siydik kislotasi diatezi, gemosideroz.

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ОСЛОЖНЕНИЯ ПЕРВИЧНОГО МИЕЛОФИБРОЗА И ТАКТИКА ИХ ЛЕЧЕНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Первичный миелофиброз (ПМФ) — редкое заболевание, число впервые выявленных больных которым в год составляет приблизительно 1: 100 000 населения. Синонимы, ранее применявшиеся для описания данного заболевания: агногенная миелоидная метаплазия, хронический идиопатический миелофиброз, остеомиелофиброз, сублейкемический миелоз.

Наиболее частыми осложнениями клинического течения ПМФ могут являться: опухолевая интоксикация, спленомегалия, анемия, инфекционные осложнения, тромбоцитопения и геморрагический синдром, наличие очагов экстрамедуллярного кроветворения, тромбозы, бластная трансформация, мочекислый диатез (вторичная подагра), вторичный гемосидероз.

В ходе изучения этого заболевания были установлены следующие результаты. Впервые как самостоятельную нозологическую форму миелолипролиферативного заболевания в 1951 г. Уильям Дамешек назвал ее идиопатической или агногенной миелоидной метаплазией. В дальнейшем сочетание заболевания с лейкоцитозом, спленомегалией и фиброзом костного мозга было описано в разных странах как первичный остеосклероз/остеомиелофиброз,

агнотенная миелоидная метаплазия, хронический идиопатический миелофиброз, остеомиелофиброз, сублейкемический миелоз. При лечении заболевания, то есть первичного миелофиброза, применение трансфузий гемокомпонентов, содержащих эритроциты, приводит к быстрому улучшению состояния больного и уменьшению проявлений анемического синдрома. В то же время длительное применение трансфузий обусловлено отсутствием активных механизмов выведения железа из организма и ограниченной способностью сохранять его в печени, когда количество трансфузий превышает 20-25 доз, при накоплении железа в органах и тканях приводит к развитию вторичного гемосидероза.

У больных может быть высокая скорость развития гемосидероза, поскольку на фоне хронической анемии увеличивается всасывание железа из желудочно-кишечного тракта. Доказано, что нарушение состояния окислительно-восстановительного процесса, стимуляции перекисного окисления липидов приводит к повреждению клеток и дисфункции внутренних органов.

Данной статье представлены рекомендации по профилактике и лечению этих осложнений.

Ключевые слова: первичный миелофиброз, опухолевая интоксикация, спленомегалия, анемия, инфекционные осложнения, геморрагический синдром, экстрамедуллярное кроветворение, тромбоз, бластная трансформация, мочекишный диатез, вторичный гемосидероз.

Кирish. Birlamchi miyelofibroz (BMF) suyak iligining o'sma kasalligi bo'lib, unda o'zgargan qon yaratuvchi o'zak hujayralar o'tmishdoshlarining ko'payishi fibrozga olib keladi va fibroz to'qimasi suyak iligining kollagen tolalari bilan almashadi.

Ilgari ushbu kasallikni tavsiflash uchun agnogen miyeloid metaplaziya, surunkali idiopatik miyelofibroz, osteomiyelofibroz, subleykemik miyeloz sinonimlari qo'llanilgan. Ba'zan xorijiy adabiyotlarda Heuck-Assman kasalligi deb ham ataladi [44].

Birlamchi miyelofibrozni o'rganish tarixi 1879 yilda Gustav Heuck tomonidan berilgan "g'alati suyak iligi leykemiya" ning ikki holatini tasvirlashdan kelib chiqadi [19]. Dastlab osteoskleroz atamasini 1907 yilda Herbert Assman qo'llagan [24]. Ushbu kasallikni birinchi marta miyeloproliferativ kasallikning mustaqil nozologik shakli sifatida 1951 yilda William Dameshek idiopatik yoki agnogen miyeloid metaplaziya deb nomlagan [14]. Keyinchalik kasallikning leykotsitoz, splenomegaliya va suyak iligi fibrozi bilan bog'liqligi turli mamlakatlarda birlamchi osteoskleroz/osteomiyelofibroz, agnogen miyeloid metaplaziya, surunkali idiopatik miyelofibroz, osteomiyelofibroz, subleykemik miyeloz deb ta'riflangan va nomlangan [1, 3, 4, 24, 44].

Tadqiqot usullari: Mazkur tadqiqot ishida bilish nazariyasining mantiqiy yondashuv, induksiya va deduksiya, qiyosiy va omilli taxlil, zamon va makon, taqqoslash, monografik ko'zatish kabi usullardan foydalanildi.

Tadqiqot natijalari:

Belgilangan maqsadga erishish va muammolarni hal qilish uchun analitik, sotsiologik va statistik tadqiqot usullaridan foydalanildi. Birlamchi miyelofibrozni klinik kechishining eng ko'p uchraydigan asoratlari quyidagilar bo'lishi mumkin: o'sma intoksikatsiyasi, splenomegaliya, anemiya, yuqumli asoratlari, trombositopeniya va gemorragik sindrom, ekstramedullar gemapoez o'choqlari, tromboz, blast transformatsiyasi, siydik kislotasi diatezi (ikkilamchi podagra), ikkilamchi gemosideroz. Quyida asoratlarning profilaktikasi va davolash bo'yicha tavsiyalar keltirilgan.

O'sma intoksikatsiyasi. Kasallik dastlab bemorlarni eng ko'p bezovta qiladigan isitma, kuchli terlash va tana vaznining kamayishi bilan namoyon bo'ladi. O'sma intoksikatsiyasining simptomlari kundalik hayotda cheklovlar va bemorlarning yashash sifatining yomonlashishiga olib keladi. Hidroksiurea bilan an'anaviy davolash, qoida kabi, o'sma intoksikatsiyasi ko'rinishining biroz kamayishiga olib keladi, ammo uni butunlay bartaraf qilmaydi. Glyukokortikoidlar va immunomodulyatorlarni qo'llanilishi, shuningdek ularning kombinatsiyasi katta ta'sirga ega, bu bemorlarning katta qismida sitokin sekretsiyasi buzilishining pasayishiga va ularning ahvolining yaxshilanishiga olib keladi. Yallig'lanishga qarshi sitokinlar darajasiga ta'sir qiluvchi eng samarali dorilar hozirgi vaqtda yanuskinaza inhibitorlari hisoblanadi, bu COMFORT-2 tekshirishi bilan

tasdiqlangan bo'lib, unda ruksolitinin va standart davolash usullari bilan davolash ta'siri taqqoslangan. Ruksolitinin guruhida intoksikatsiya belgilari intensivligining statistik jihatdan sezilarli darajada kamayishi va yashash sifati ko'rsatkichlarining yaxshilanishi kuzatilgan, o'sha paytda standart terapiya ushbu ko'rsatkichlarga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatmagan [18, 45].

Splenomegaliya. Ekstramedullar gemapoez sababli taloq o'lchamining kattalashishi ham birlamchi miyelofibroznining ko'p uchraydigan ko'rinishlaridan biri hisoblanadi va bemorlarni davolashda dolzarb muammo bo'lishi mumkin. Qorin bo'shlig'ining kattalashishi va shishishi, erta to'yinish hissi, qorindagi og'riqlar kabi simptomlardan tashqari, splenomegaliya ko'pincha taloq infarkti, qorin bo'shlig'i a'zolarining siqilishi, portal gipertenziya rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Gipersplenizm sindromi qonning katta miqdorini sekvestrlash, autoimmunizatsiya rivojlanishi tufayli sitopeniyaning namoyon bo'lishini kuchayishiga olib keladi. Splenomegaliyani davolash dorilar yordamida yoki jarrohlik usuli bilan o'tkazilishi mumkin. Ko'pincha gidroksiurea qo'llaniladi, bu taloq o'lchamining kichrayishiga olib kelishi mumkin [26].

Biroq, gidroksiurea bilan davolash sitopeniyaning kuchayishiga olib kelishi mumkin, davolashning ta'siri beqaror, ko'pincha splenomegaliya qovurg'a yoyidan 10 sm dan kam bo'lgan bemorlarda va JAK2V617F mutatsiyasining mavjudligida kuzatiladi [39]. Gidroksiureaga nisbatan chidamsizlik yoki rezistentlik rivojlansa, busulfan yoki melfalan qo'llanilishi mumkin, ularning ko'p uchraydigan gematologik toksikligini hisobga olish kerak. Bemorlarning kichik bir qismida (20 foizdan kam) taloq o'lchamining kichrayishi talidomidning kichik dozalarida kuzatiladi [8]. Kladrinin ijobiy terapevtik ta'sir bilan qo'llaniladi, bu bemorlarning ko'pchiligida taloq o'lchamining kichrayishiga olib keladi, ammo yaqqol sitopeniya bilan ham bog'liq [16].

Splenektomiya dorilar bilan davolash samarasiz yoki bardoshlilik yaxshi bo'lmasa, medikamentoz terapiyaga muqobil davolash hisoblanadi. Splenektomiya uchun ko'rsatmalar massiv splenomegaliya, kaxeziya, portal gipertenziya qizilo'ngach va oshqozon venalarining varikoz kengayishi, transfuziyon terapiyaga qaramlik bilan bog'liq anemiya hisoblanadi. Splenektomiya og'riqni, qorin damlashini va tez to'yinganlik hissi simptomlarini yengillashtiradi, tana vaznining yetishmasligini kamaytiradi. Gemoglobinning ko'payishi bemorlarning yarmida kuzatilishi mumkin, splenektomiya qilingan bemorlarning 30 foizidan sal kamroq qismida trombositopeniya kamayadi. Shu bilan birga, splenomegaliya, portal gipertenziyaning mavjudligi, sitopeniya va gemostazning buzilishi operatsiyani bajarishda katta qiyinchiliklarga olib keladi va bemorlarning 30-50 foizida operatsiyadan keyingi asoratlarga, 5-10 foizida esa o'limga olib keladi.

Taloq sohasiga nur terapiya medikamentoz terapiyaning samarasizligi va splenektomiyaga qarshi ko'rsatma yoki rad etilishida qo'llaniladi. Nur terapiya splenomegaliyaning klinik belgilarini va o'lchamini o'rtacha darajada kamaytirishi mumkin, Nur terapiya patologik simptomlarni to'liq bartaraf qilmaydi, natijasi beqaror va faqat bir necha oy davom etadi, qoida kabi, sitopeniyaning kuchayishiga olib keladi, bu bemorlarning taxminan 10-15 foizini o'limini sababi bo'ladi. Bunday holda, nur terapiya mahalliy fibrozning rivojlanishiga, qorin bo'shlig'i va qo'shni a'zolar bilan bitishmalarning paydo bo'lishiga olib keladi, bu esa keyinchalik splenektomiyani texnik jihatdan juda qiyinlashtiradi [26].

Anemiya. Birlamchi miyelofibroznining eng keng tarqalgan asoratlaridan biri bu anemiya hisoblanadi, u ko'pincha kasallikning boshlanishida kuzatiladi va BMF tashxisini qo'yish uchun asos bo'ladi. Anemiyani davolash uchun kislorod tanqisligini va hayot uchun xavfli holatlarni bartaraf qilish uchun ko'pincha eritrotsitlar massasi transfuziyasi o'tkazilishi kerak. Davolashni rejalashtirishda BMF anemiyasi polietologik xarakterga ega bo'lishi mumkinligini va boshqa moddalar qatori vitaminlar va mikroelementlarning yetishmasligi, shuningdek, yo'ldosh kasalliklarning natijasi bo'lishi mumkinligini yodda tutish kerak. Shuning uchun tekshirish doirasida Hb miqdorini va eritrotsitlar sonini aniqlashdan tashqari, retikulotsitlarni hisoblash, temir matabolizmi ko'rsatkichlarini (zardobdagi temir, transferrin, ferritin), vitamin B₁₂ va foliy kislotasi, eritropoetin miqdorini aniqlash kerak.

Temir tanqisligida, asosan, kuniga 4-5 mg/kg yoki kamida 200 mg dozada og'iz orqali temir dorilarini buyurish tavsiya etiladi: Sorbifer-durules, Maltofer, Ferrum-lek (ayniqsa oshqozon-ichak trakti kasalliklarida), Ferlatum, Ferretab fenyuls, Tardiferon, Ferrogradumet va boshqalar. Klinik qon

tekshiruv va temir metabolizmini nazorat qilish davolashni har oyida tavsiya etiladi. Davolash samaradorligi mezoni – davolanishni bir oyi davomida Hb miqdorini me'yorga yoki dastlabki ko'rsatkichidan 15-20 g/l dan yuqori darajaga ko'tarilishi hisoblanadi. Hb miqdori normallashtirishdan so'ng, organizmdagi temir zaxiralarini to'ldirish uchun uning dorilarini qabul qilishni taxminan uch oy davom ettirish tavsiya etiladi. Kelajakda vaqti-vaqti bilan 3-6 oyda bir marta temir metabolizmi ko'rsatkichlarini nazorat qilish kerak [2].

Vitamin B₁₂ tanqisligida siyanokobalaminni parenteral yuborish anemiyaning og'irligiga mos dozada tavsiya etiladi. Davolashning birinchi oyida taxminiy dozalar quyidagicha: engil anemiyada kuniga 200 mkg, o'rtacha anemiyada kuniga 400 mkg va og'ir anemiyada kuniga 600 mkg. Siyanokobalaminning qo'llab-quvvatlovchi dozasi oyiga 200-500 mkg ni tashkil qiladi [2].

Folik kislotasi tanqisligi anemiyasida foliy kislotasi buyuriladi, malabsorbtsiya bilan tez-tez uchraydigan kasalliklarni hisobga olgan holda taxminiy dozasi kuniga 5 mg ni tashkil qiladi. Hb ko'rsatkichi normallashtirishdan so'ng, kuniga 1 mg dozada qo'llab - quvvatlovchi terapiyasini o'tkazish tavsiya etiladi [2].

Eritropoezning o'ziga xos rag'batlantirilishi, shuningdek, surunkali kasalliklar, shu jumladan ko'pincha buyrak patologiya bilan birga keladigan anemiyaning mavjudligini hisobga olgan holda, eritropoezni rag'batlantiruvchi dorilar yordamida ham o'tkazilishi mumkin. Eritropoetinlar bilan davolashning uzoq muddatli natijalarini tahlil qilish, birlamchi miyelofibroza blast transformatsiyasi xavfini oshirmasligini ko'rsatdi. Gemotransfuziyaga qaramlik [20] va davolash boshlanishidan oldin endogen eritropoetin darajasi prognostik ahamiyatga ega, uning qiymati 125 XB/l dan yuqori bo'lsa, natija olish ehtimoli past [11], Davolashning ijobiy natijasi bemorlarning taxminan yarmida kuzatiladi va o'rtacha bir yil davom etadi [20].

Birlamchi miyelofibroza anemiya rivojlanishining immunologik mexanizmlariga ta'sir qilish va sitokin muvozanatini normallashtirish uchun past dozada glyukokortikoidlar, androgenlar va immunomodulyatorlar qo'llanilishi mumkin. Immunomodulyatorlar va glyukokortikoidlarni birgalikda qo'llashda eng yuqori samaradorlik va eng yaxshi tolerantlik kuzatiladi [21, 27, 28, 33, 34, 41]. Immunomodulyatorlardan foydalanganda gemoglobinning ko'payishi bemorlarning 20-40 foizida kuzatiladi [42]. 5q o'chirilishi mavjud bemorlarda lenalidomid qo'llanilganda sezilarli darajada yuqori samaradorlik kuzatiladi [28, 33, 40].

Yuqumli asoratlar. Ba'zan kasallikning namoyon bo'lishi leykopeniya va neytropeniya BMF bilan kasallangan bemorlarda yuqumli asoratlarning ko'payishiga olib keladi. Immunitet tanqisligi rivojlanishi patogenezning asosiy bo'g'imlaridan biri bo'lgan sitokin muvozanati ham ma'lum hissa qo'shadi. Birlamchi miyelofibrozni davolash uchun qo'llaniladigan dorilar neytropeniyaning kuchaytirishi va immun tizimning hujayralararo hamkorligini bostirishi mumkin. Bemorlarda yuqumli jarayonlar ikkilamchi immunitet tanqisligi sababli yuzaga keladi va ko'pincha atipik tarzda sodir bo'ladi. Isitma, shu jumladan febril isitma, shuningdek, o'sma intoksikatsiyasining simptomlari bo'lishi mumkin, shuning uchun yuqumli asoratlarning debyuti o'tkazib yuborilishi mumkin.

Yuqumli asoratlarning tashxisi anamnezni sinchkovlik bilan yig'ishga asoslangan bo'lib, infeksiyaning mumkin bo'lgan manbasini aniqlash, shu jumladan a'zolarni vizualizatsiya qilish (nur diagnostika va endoskopiya usullari) va patogenni aniqlash uchun material to'plash (yuvish, biologik suyuqliklarni tekshirish va boshqalar). Immunitet tanqisligida bakteremiya va virusemiya rivojlanishida mikroorganizmlarning qonga tez kirib borishi ehtimolini hisobga olish kerak. BMF bilan kasallangan bemorda isitma bo'lsa, qon ekmasini tekshirish majburiydir, u zamonaviy usullardan (PZR va boshqalar) foydalanganda patogenni bir necha soat ichida aniqlay oladi. Ekmalar bir vaqtning o'zida bakteriyalar va zamburug'lar uchun tanlangan muhitda o'tkazilishi kerak. Kateter bilan bog'liq infeksiyalarni istisno qilish uchun markaziy va periferik vena kateterlaridan bir vaqtning o'zida parallel namuna olish majburiydir [31]. Keyinchalik davriy qaytalanuvchi infeksiya o'choqlarini surunkali kechishi ehtimoli tez-tez uchraydi. Bunday holda, anamnezni sinchkovlik bilan o'rganish infeksiyalarni qiyosiy tashxislashda yordam beradi. Kasallik va davolanish tufayli ikkilamchi immun tanqisligi fonida opportunistik infeksiyalar (atipik bakterial, zamburug'li va boshqalar) ehtimoli ham yuqori.

Patogenni aniqlashdan oldin, bemorlarga ko'pincha kombinatsiyalangan immun tanqisligi mavjudligi sababli, yuqumli patogenlarning butun spektrini maksimal dozalarda qoplaydigan antibiotiklardan foydalangan holda empirik antibakterial terapiya buyurilishi kerak. Empirik antibakterial terapiyaning samaradorlik mezoni bemorning ahvolini yaxshilash yoki barqarorlashtirish, terapiyaning 3-5 kunida infeksiya va isitmaning klinik ko'rinishlarining yo'qolishi hisoblanadi. Agar antibakterial terapiya natijasi yetarli bo'lmasa, klinik ma'lumotlar va antibiotiklarga sezgirlik uchun mikroflorani tekshirish natijalarini hisobga olgan holda boshqa antibiotiklarni yoki ularning kombinatsiyasini buyurish kerak. Patogenni aniqlab, uning individual sezgirligi aniqlanilgandan keyin, antibakterial terapiyani eng samarali dorini tanlash orqali o'tkazish kerak [2, 5, 13, 17].

Biroq, bemorlarning katta qismida yuqumli asoratlarda patogenni aniqlash choralari natija bermaydi va empirik antibakterial terapiyaning dastlabki sxemasi yetarli darajada samarali bo'lmaydi. Bunday hollarda yuqumli asoratlarning virusli va mikotik genezini istisno qilish kerak. Agar bemorning ahvoli yomonlashsa, isitmaning 4-kunidan keyin itrakonazol (salbiy inotrop ta'sirga ega), vorikonazol, posakonazol, amfoterisin kabi dorilar bilan faol, shu jumladan zamburug'larga qarshi antimikotik terapiya kaspofungin, mikafungin turli kombinatsiyalarda belgilanishi kerak, ayniqsa isitma boshlanishidan oldin antimikotik profilaktika o'tkazilmagan bo'lsa [10, 32, 37]. Herpes simplex viruslari va sitomegalovirusga qarshi antivirus terapiya (asiklovir, valatsiklovir, gansiklovir, valgansiklovir, famsiklovir) serologik yoki PZR usullari bilan tasdiqlangunga qadar, yuqumli asoratning xarakterli klinik belgilari (teri va shilliq qavatning pufakchali zararlanishi, nekrozli yaralar, ezofagit, atipik o'pka infiltratlari, retinit) mavjud bo'lganda buyurilishi mumkin. [6, 46].

Neytropeniya fonida yuzaga kelgan yuqumli asoratlarda kuniga 5 mkg/kg G-KRO, shuningdek, 3-5 kun davomida 0,2–0,5 g/kg dozalarda inson immunoglobulinidan foydalanish, zaharsizlantirish va dori-darmonlarga sezgirlikni yaxshilash uchun plazmaferez o'tkazish mumkin [2, 17, 36].

Trombotsitopeniya va gemorragik sindrom. Trombotsitopeniya ko'pincha BMF kechishini murakkablashtirishi mumkin, ayniqsa suyak iligini yaqqol fibrozi va gemapoezning buzulishi mavjud bo'lganda. Trombotsitopeniyaning klinik ko'rinishi qon ketishining o'z-o'zidan rivojlanishi ko'rinishidagi gemorragik sindrom hisoblanadi.

Gemorragik sindrom rivojlanishiga ikkilamchi koagulopatiya ham sabab bo'lishi mumkin, bu portal gipertenziya va ekstramedullar gemapoez o'choqlari tomonidan parenximaning zararlanishi sababli jigar qon ivish omillarini ishlab chiqarishning buzilishi bilan bog'liq. Trombotsitopeniyaning davolash taktikasi uning sababini bartaraf etish va gemorragik sindromning profilaktikasiga qaratilgan bo'lishi kerak. Birlamchi miyelofibroza trombotsitopeniya rivojlanishining sabablari trombotsitlar ishlab chiqarishning kamayishi va ularning parchalanishining ko'payishi bo'lishi mumkin. Trombotsitlar hosil bo'lishining kamayishi ko'pincha normal gemapoezni qisilishi va suyak iligi fibrozining rivojlanishida patologik klonning faol ko'payishi bilan bog'liq. Immunomodulyatorlar [8, 9, 41] va yanuskinaza ingibitorlari [18, 45] ham bu jarayonga patogenetik ta'sir ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Trombotsitopeniya splenomegaliya, trombotsitlar va megakaryotsitlarga qarshi autoantitanachalarning hosil bo'lishi sababli taloqda ularning parchalanishining kuchayishi sababli yuzaga kelishi mumkin. Asoratlarning profilaktikasi vitamin C, rutin, etamzilat (ditsinon) dorilarini buyurish va xavf omillarini istisno qilish orqali qon tomir devorining holatini yaxshilashga qaratilgan bo'lishi kerak – venoz bosimni normallashtirish (beta-blokatorlar, kaltsiy kanallari blokatorlari, qon tomir shunti yordamida portal gipertenziyani kamaytirish), shilliq qavat zararlanishining oldini olish (burun shilliq qavatining namlanishi, yaralarni oldini olish uchun sekretolitiklar. oshqozon yarasi, gemorroy uchun mahalliy terapiya). Trombotsitlar kontsentratsiyasini transfuziyasi qisqa muddatli ta'sirga ega va faqat gemorragik sindrom mavjud bo'lganda yoki qon ketish xavfi yuqori bo'lsa tavsiya etiladi, bundan tashqari, takroriy transfuziyalarda, autoimmunizatsiya tufayli transfuziyaga rezistentlik rivojlanishi mumkin [47]. TITQIS va gemostazning plazma bo'g'inini buzilishlarini davolash uchun yangi muzlatilgan plazmani yetarli dozalarda quyish va rekombinant koagulyatsion omillarni belgilash ham qo'llaniladi [2, 4].

Ekstramedullar gemapoezning o'choqlari. Birlamchi miyelofibrozda qon yaratish a'zolaridan tashqarida deyarli har doim qon yaratish o'choqlari rivojlanadi. Ularning paydo bo'lishiga o'sma sababli stromal mikromuhitning qo'pol buzilishi va natijada o'tmishdosh hujayralar, shu jumladan gemapoetik o'zak hujayralar (GO'H) periferik qon oqimiga kirib borishi sabab bo'ladi [12, 25].

Ekstramedullar gemapoez o'choqlarini hosil bo'lishida GO'H ko'payish imkoniyati birinchi navbatda jigar va taloqda mavjud bo'lib, unda gemapoez embrion va prenatal davrda sodir bo'ladi. Ammo kasallikning uzoq davom etishida ekstramedullar gemapoezning o'choqlari boshqa a'zolar va to'qimalarda ham rivojlanishi mumkin. Shunday qilib, jigar va taloqdan tashqari, gemapoezning ekstramedullar o'choqlari qorin pardada astsit rivojlanishi bilan, o'pka gipertenziyasi va ekssudativ plevrit shakllanishi bilan o'pkada, limfa tugunlarda ularning kattalashishi va asosiy a'zolar va tomirlarning siqilishi bilan, ko'krak va bel umurtqalarida umurtqa pog'onasining siqilishi bilan, asab tomirlarining siqilishi va neyropatik og'riq bilan qo'l - oyoqlarda paydo bo'ladi [43].

Ekstramedullar gemapoez o'choqlarining paydo bo'lishi a'zolar tuzilishining zararlanishi va qon oqimining buzilishi (portal gipertenziya, ekssudativ plevrit va astsit) bilan birga keladi. Mahalliy yallig'lanishni keltirib chiqaradigan o'sma hujayralari tomonidan ishlab ajratiladigan sitokinlar ichki a'zolarining disfunktsiyasiga ma'lum darajada hissa qo'shadi. Ekstramedullar gemapoezning simptomsiz o'choqlarining mavjudligi tizimli davolash o'tkazishni talab qilmaydi. Ushbu o'choqlarning rivojlanishiga asosiy patogenetik hissa hujayralarning o'zaro ta'sirining buzilishi va sitokinning patologik sekretsiyasi ekanligini hisobga olib, ushbu asoratlarning profilaktikasi va patogenetik davolash uchun glyukokortikoidlar va yanuskinaza inhibitorlari bilan birgalikda iImmunomodulyatorlar eng samarali bo'lishi mumkin. Ekstramedullar gemapoez o'choqlari bilan bog'liq mahalliy klinik simptomlarning mavjudligi past dozalarda mahalliy nur terapiya o'tkazishga ko'rsatma hisoblanadi (bit martalik dozasi 1 Gr, kurs dozasi 10 Gr) [22, 30, 38]. Bo'shliqlarda suyuqlik to'planganda plevra punktsiyalari va paratsentezni plevrodez bilan qo'llash mumkin.

Trombozlar. Birlamchi miyelofibrozning kechishi tromboz rivojlanish xavfi va yurak-qon tomir kasalliklarining kuchayishi bilan bog'liq. BMF bilan kasallangan bemorlarda tromboz uchun tasdiqlangan xavf omillari yoshi 60 dan oshgan va JAK2V617F mutatsiyasi mavjud bemorlar, ayniqsa leykotsitoz bilan birgalikda kelishi hisoblanadi [7]. Essensial trombositemiya va haqiqiy politsitemiyada tromboz rivojlanish xavfini kamaytiradigan gidroksiurea va trombositlar miqdorining kamayishi birlamchi miyelofibrozda ham xuddi shunday ta'sir ko'rsatishi taxmin qilinmoqda. Antiagregant agentlar – asetilsalitsil kislotasini buyurish orqali trombozning oldini olish trombositlar miqdori $50 \times 10^9/l$ dan yuqori bo'lgan barcha birlamchi miyelofibroz bilan kasallangan bemorlariga tavsiya etiladi [43]. Tromboz xavfini kamaytirishning istiqboli yanuskinaza inhibitorlari, xususan ruksolitinibdan foydalanish hisoblanadi. O'tkazilgan ikkita klinik tadqiqotda (COMFORT-1 va COMFORT-2) ruksolitinib leykotsitlar va trombositlar miqdorini sezilarli darajada, shu bilan birga JAK2V617F allel yuklamasining o'rtacha kamaytiradi [18, 45].

Trombozdan keyin ikkilamchi profilaktika qon ko'rsatkichlarini, qon ivish tizimining ko'rsatkichlarini normallashtirishga qaratiladi va qon ivish tizimi nazorati ostida bevosita va bilvosita antikoagulyantlar bilan antikoagulyant terapiya ko'rsatmalariga muvofiq tayinlanadi.

Blast transformatsiyasi. Birlamchi miyelofibrozda o'sma klonining uzoq muddatli proliferatsiyasida qo'shimcha mutatsiyalarning to'planishi o'smaning xavfli jarayonga o'tishiga va kasallikning oxirgi bosqichi – blast transformatsiyasining rivojlanishiga olib kelishi mumkin.

Kasallikning boshlanishidan blast transformatsiyasining rivojlanishigacha bo'lgan vaqt bir-ikki yildan o'n yilgacha sezilarli darajada farq qilishi mumkin. Blast transformatsiyasining rivojlanish vaqtidagi bunday farq kasallikning boshlanish vaqtini belgilashning noaniqligi bilan bog'liq.

Hozirgi vaqtda kasallikni blast krizining profilaktikasi uchun isbotlangan vositalar, uning paydo bo'lish mexanizmlari yetarli darajada o'rganilmaganligi sababli ishlab chiqilmagan. Randomizatsiyalangan sinovda an'anaviy terapiya bilan solishtirganda bemorlarning umumiy yashovchanligini statistik jihatdan sezilarli darajada oshiradigan birinchi vosita yanuskinaza inhibitori – ruksolitinib hisoblanadi (COMFORT-1 va COMFORT-2 tadqiqotlari) [18, 45].

Blast transformatsiyasining rivojlanishida prognoz odatda salbiy bo'ladi, o'rtacha yashovchanlik bir necha oyni tashkil qiladi. Davolash taktikasi bemorlarning yoshi va yo'ldosh kasalligi hisobga olgan holda belgilanadi. Umumiy somatik ahvoli saqlanib qolgan bemorlarda o'tkir leykozni davolash sxemalari bo'yicha kimyoterapiya kursini o'tkazishga urinish mumkin, bu bemorlarning kichik qismiga vaqtinchalik natija beradi. Jiddiy komorbidlik va BMF asoratlari mavjud keksa bemorlarga cheklovchi palliativ monokimyoterapiyani o'tkazish va glyukokortikoidlarning kichik dozalarini buyurish tavsiya etiladi. Ushbu chora-tadbirlar bemorning yashash sifatini yaxshilash maqsadida o'sma o'sishini bostirish va asoratlarni (gemokomponentlarni quyish, yuqumli asoratlarni davolash va boshqalar) bartaraf qilishga qaratilgan [2, 4].

Siydik kislotasi diatezi (ikkilamchi podagra). Katta o'sma massasining mavjudligi va qon hujayralarining bir qismini doimiy ravishda parchalanishi, lizisga uchragan hujayralarning yadrolaridan ajralib chiqadigan DNKning ko'p miqdordagi azotli asoslarini qayta ishlash zarurligiga olib keladi.

Purin nukleotidlaridan hosil bo'lgan siydik kislotasini qayta ishlashning asosiy fermenti gipoksantin-guanin-fosforibosiltransferaza bo'lib, u sezilarli o'zgaruvchan populyatsion faollikka ega. Shu munosabat bilan, BMF bilan kasallangan bemorlarning ma'lum bir qismida ikkilamchi giperurikemiya rivojlanishi va podagra o'xshash simptomlar aniqlanishi mumkin. Metatarsofalangeal bo'g'imlarning zararlanishi bilan klassik bo'g'in sindromdan tashqari, buyraklardagi urat toshlarining cho'kishi va pielonefrit rivojlanishi bilan siydik tosh kasalligining rivojlanishi kuzatilishi mumkin. To'qimalarda siydik kislotasining cho'kishi og'riqsiz tugunlar – tofus shakllanishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Ushbu asoratning profilaktikasi uchun birinchi navbatda siydik kislota miqdorini dastlabki tashxislaash va davolash paytida leykotsitlar soni va taloq hajmi normallasguncha kuzatib borish kerak. Giperurikemiya simptomlarining namoyon bo'lishining profilaktikasi uchun buyraklarda siydik kislota kristallarining cho'kishini bartaraf qilish uchun gidrokarbonat mineral suvlarini tayinlash va allopurinolni kuniga 300-600 mg dozada, zardobdagi siydik kislota miqdoriga qarab dozani to'g'irlash bilan yetarli darajada o'sma lizisining gidratsiyasini oldini olish mumkin.

Podagra hurujining rivojlanishida nosteroid yallig'lanishga qarshi dorilar og'iz orqali va mahalliy malham, gellar (Nimesulid, Selekoksib, Meloksikam, Diklofenak, Ibuprofen va boshqalar) ko'rinishida bo'g'im sohasiga qo'llaniladi. Siydik tosh kasalligida, surunkali piyelonefritning qaytalanishini profilaktikasi uchun uroseptiklar (Nitroksolin, Pipemid kislota, fitodorilar va boshqalar), piyelonefritning bakterial qaytalanishida keng spektrli antibiotiklar: ftorxinolonlar, makrolidlar, aminoglikozidlar nitrofuran seriyasining mikroblarga qarshi dorilari qo'llaniladi. Qonda siydik kislota miqdorini tez kamaytirishga erishish uchun afferent usullardan foydalanish — qonni ultrafiltratsiyasi krioplazmosorbtsiya bilan o'tkazish mumkin.

Ikkilamchi gemosideroz. Birlamchi miyelofibrozni davolashda tarkibida eritrotsitlar mavjud gemokomponentlar transfuziyalaridan foydalanish bemorning ahvolini tezda yaxshilashga va anemik sindromning namoyon bo'lishining kamayishiga olib keladi. Shu bilan birga, organizmda temirni yo'q qilishning faol mexanizmlari yo'qligi va uni jigarda saqlash imkoniyati cheklanganligi sababli transfuziyalardan uzoq muddat foydalanish, transfuziyalar soni 20-25 dozadan ortiq bo'lganda, a'zolar va to'qimalarda temirning to'planishi bilan tavsiflanadigan ikkilamchi gemosideroz rivojlanishiga olib keladi. Bemorlarda gemosideroz rivojlanish darajasi yuqori bo'lishi mumkin, chunki surunkali anemiya fonida oshqozon-ichak traktidan temirning so'rilishi kuchayadi. Oksidlanish – tiklanish holatining buzilishi, lipidlarning perekisli oksidlanishining rag'batlantirilishi hujayralarning zararlanishiga va ichki a'zolarining disfunktsiyasiga olib keladi.

Gemosiderozning eng keng tarqalgan klinik ko'rinishlari yurak, jigar, oshqozon osti bezi, ko'z to'r pardasining zararlanishi bilan bog'liq.

Temir zaxiralarini nazorat qilish eritrotsitlarning 10 dan ortiq dozalarini transfuziyasidan keyin o'tkazilishi kerak. Temir metabolizmini baholashning eng qulay usuli bu zardobda ferritinini aniqlash hisoblanadi. 1000 ng/ml dan yuqori daraja temirning haddan tashqari yuklanishini ko'rsatadi. Ferritinni aniqlash laboratoriya amaliyotida osonlikcha o'tkaziladi, ammo bir qator kamchiliklarga ega. Birinchidan, ferritin miqdorining to'qima temir zaxiralari bilan yetarlicha yaqin korrelyatsiyasi.

Qon zardobidagi ferritin kontsentratsiyasi yallig'lanish, jigar funktsiyasining buzilishi, C gipovitaminozda ham o'zgarishi mumkin. Temir miqdorini baholashning boshqa usullari (jigar biopsiyasida temirni quruq moddada aniqlash, T2 rejimida jigar MRT) aniqroq, ammo mahalliy amaliyotda hali ham mavjud emas.

Temirning haddan tashqari yuklanishini xelator (deferaziroks, deferapiron) terapiyani qo'llash orqali bartaraf qilish mumkin [23] va agar ilgari xelatatorlarni tayinlash uchun ko'rsatma gemosideroz (20-25 dozadan ortiq gemotransfuziya, ferritin 1000 ng/ml yoki mkg/l dan ortiq) mavjudligi bo'lsa, hozirgi vaqtda temir xelatatorlarini profilaktik maqsadda tayinlash va gemotransfuziyaga qaramlikning paydo bo'lishida ferritinni nazorat qilish hisoblanadi. Temir xelatatorlaridan hozirgi vaqtda faqat Deferaziroks (Eksijad®) ro'yxatga olingan. Ilgari keng qo'llanilgan deferoksamin ishlab chiqarilishi to'xtatilgan. Deferaziroksga muqobil dori deferapiron ro'yxatga olinmagan. Deferaziroksning boshlang'ich dozasi (Exijad®) kuniga 10-20 mg/kg hisoblanadi. Doza miqdori ferritin darajasiga qarab belgilanadi (2500 ng/ml dan kam yoki undan ko'p).

Xelator terapiyaning samaradorligi mezoni a'zolar zararlanishi rivojlanishining yo'qligi va ferritin darajasining 2500 ng/ml dan kam bo'lishi hisoblanadi. Ferritin darajasini nazorat qilish har 2-3 oyda bir marta o'tkazilishi kerak. Agar samarasiz bo'lsa, deferaziroks dozasi kuniga 30 mg/kg gacha oshirish mumkin. Shuni esda tutish kerakki, ferritin kamayganidan keyin, ammo transfuziyon qaramlik saqlanib qolganda, temirning haddan tashqari yuklanishini takrorlanishining oldini olish uchun temir xelatatorlarini qabul qilishni davom ettirish tavsiya etiladi. Ba'zida xelatorlar yordamida temir haddan tashqari yuklangan BMF bilan kasallangan bemorlarni davolashda bemorlarda aylanuvchi CD34+ o'tmishdoshlari darajasining kamayishi kuzatiladi, bu qon quyishga qaramlikning kamayishi bilan qon ko'rsatkichlarining yaxshilanishiga olib kelgan [15, 29, 35]. Buning sababi shundaki, deferaziroksning o'zi NF-κB yadro omilining ingibitori bo'lishi mumkin va shu bilan o'sma klonining ko'payishini kamaytiradi. Suyak iligi gemosiderozining kamayishi gemapoez funktsiyasini ham yaxshilashi mumkin.

Xulosa. Bizning tadqiqotimizga ko'ra, birlamchi miyelofibroz, uzoq o'rganish tarixiga ega bo'lishiga qaramay, hozirgi vaqtgacha tashxis qo'yilgan paytdan boshlab o'rtacha umr ko'rish davomiyligi taxminan 6-7 yilni tashkil qiladigan og'ir kasallik hisoblanadi. Kasallikning odatiy kechishi o'sma massasining progressiv o'sishi, o'sma intoksikatsiyasi simptomlarining paydo bo'lishi, jigar va taloqda ekstramedullar qon yaratish o'choqlarining rivojlanishi bilan bog'liq. Keyinchalik, suyak iligidagi fibroz va osteosklerozning ko'payishi ko'rinishidagi o'zgarishlar qon yaratish plasdarmining kamayishi va anemiya, leykopeniya va trombositopeniya rivojlanishiga olib keladi. O'sma klonining uzoq muddatli ko'payishi qo'shimcha mutatsiyalarga va kasallikning blast krizini rivojlanish ehtimoliga olib keladi. Kasallikning asoratlarini davolash uchun gemokomponentlar transfuziyasi, qon yaratilishini rag'batlantiruvchi dorilar, jarrohlik usullari va nur terapiya qo'llaniladi.

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